

Table 1. Comparison of grain yield between Peiliangyou Teqing and check Shanyou 63. HRVRT, Hunan, China, 1992-93.

Year	Locations (no.)	Combinations and varieties (no.)	Replications (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Peiliangyou Teqing over check ^a	
				Peiliangyou Teqing	Shanyou 63	t/ha	%
1992	7	6	3	9.5	9.1	0.43**	4.7
1993	6	9	3	7.7	7.3	0.43 ^{ns}	5.8

^a** = significant at 1% level by Duncan's SSR test; ns = not significant by Duncan's SSR test.

Table 2. Economic traits and grain quality of Peiliangyou Teqing. HRVRT, Hunan, China, 1992-93.

Year	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Filled spikelets (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Brown rice (%)	Milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Chalkiness (%)
1992	136.7	97.5	140.1	87.9	23.4	79.4	69.8	45.6	5.3
1993	135.8	105.6	144.5	84.6	22.3	82.8	70.6	62.2	-
Mean	136.3	101.6	142.3	86.3	22.9	81.1	70.2	53.9	5.3

Pei'ai 64S has a low critical sterility temperature of 23.3 °C under short daylength. When the daily mean temperature is more than 23.3 °C, it is completely sterile; when the daily mean temperature is less than 23.3 °C, it becomes partially fertile, thus producing selfed seeds. It has also wide compatibility, and when crossed with either indica or japonica rices, it shows generally normal pollen and seed fertility in the F₁ hybrids. Because Pei'ai 64S has a low critical sterility temperature (23.3 °C under short daylength), it is difficult to multiply. Yield during seed multiplication was usually unstable because of fluctuating temperatures, but more than 2.25 t/ha may be obtained by irrigating with low-temperature water.

Teqing, the paternal line, is a high-yielding indica variety developed by the Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences and being grown in southern China.

In the 1992 Hunan Rice Variety Regional Trial (HRVRT) for medium rice, Peiliangyou Teqing yielded an average of 9.5 t/ha across seven locations (Table 1), 4.7% (significant at 1% level) higher than the check hybrid Shanyou 63 and the best of six combinations or varieties tested. In the 1993 HRVRT, its yield averaged 7.7 t/ha across six locations, 5.8% higher than that of Shanyou 63 and the best of nine combinations or varieties tested.

The combination was cultivated in demonstration plots in 1991. Planted on 667 ha in 1992 and 1,333 ha in 1993 in Hunan Province, it yielded 7.5-9.0 t/ha.

Jinuo 1: a new glutinous japonica variety with high yield and good quality

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Jinuo 1 is a new glutinous japonica rice variety derived from JG954 (58nuo/Nonghu 6//BL-7) using the system selection method. It was released in Mar 1992 as a special rice variety.

Jinuo 1 is photoperiod-insensitive and has a 170 d growth duration. It is 100 cm tall, with panicle length of 16.5 cm, and a 1,000-grain weight of 28 g. Its fertility is more than 85%. The yield potential of Jinuo 1 is high and stable, 0.9-32.6%

Yield potential of Jinuo 1 in the Rice Regional Trials of northern China, 1992.

Site	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check ^a (%)
Beijing	7.5	23.4
Zhuozhou, Hebei	9.5	32.6
Tianjin	8.0	7.32
Baoding, Hebei	10.6	31.78
Tanghai, Hebei	8.9	0.9
Liaoning	5.3	1.15

^aZhonghua 8.

The combination matures in 136 d as a medium rice crop (Table 2). It is moderately resistant to blast and bacterial blight. Peiliangyou Teqing is about 100 cm tall and has good plant type, strong tillering ability, sturdy stature, dark green leaves, and large panicles. Its seed setting rate is more than 80%, with a mean of 142 spikelets/panicle and a 1,000-grain weight of 23 g. The yields of brown, milled, and head rice were 81.1%, 70.2%, and 53.9%, respectively. Chalkiness was 5.3% and the eating quality acceptable. ■

more than the check in the Rice Regional Trials of northern China in 1992. Its yield stability was the best among the new varieties being tested (see table).

Jinuo 1 is moderately resistant to leaf blast and bacterial blight and is resistant to whitebacked planthopper. Its resistance to lodging is very strong because of its firm stems.

Most of the grain quality characteristics of Jinuo 1 meet China's national index for good quality rice. Hulling recovery was 84.5%; milling recovery, 76.0%; grain length, 5.1 mm; grain length-breadth ratio, 1.6; amylose content, 1.2%; and protein content, 7.4%.

Jinuo 1 is planted on about 6,000 ha. It is the first time that a high-yielding glutinous japonica rice variety with good quality was selected in northern China. ■